

Detecting Agro-Pastoral Abandonment: A Sentinel-2 Multi-Temporal Phenology Approach for Sub-Mediterranean Landscapes

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Abstract: The cessation of agro-pastoral management in sub-Mediterranean mountains drives secondary succession from dry grasslands to closed woodlands, threatening biodiversity and agricultural capacity. This paper presents a Google Earth Engine methodology mapping abandonment status and successional velocity at cadastral resolution using Sentinel-2 (2018–2024). A deterministic cascade exploits the seasonal contrast where managed grasslands are drought-dormant in summer while evergreen maquis remains active, combined with Seasonal Amplitude, Mann–Kendall trend analysis, and the JRC Global Human Settlement Layer, requiring no labelled training data. Applied to Italy's Monti Prenestini district, the method achieves 85.8% overall accuracy ($\kappa = 0.82$). Encroached parcels, treated here as a priority restoration class for the study area, occupy moderate, machinery-accessible slopes similar to currently managed land, while most abandoned parcels sit on steeper terrain that constrains recovery. The resulting ranked cadastral database supports parcel-level prioritisation of interventions.

Keywords: Sentinel-2; land abandonment; agricultural land; Mediterranean; NDVI time series.

1 Introduction

The sub-Mediterranean mountain landscapes of central Italy have experienced rural depopulation since the mid-twentieth century, driving extensive passive secondary succession across marginal agricultural land (Navarro and Pereira 2012). While ecologically valuable at a continental scale, this succession, from actively managed dry grassland to encroaching maquis and secondary woodland, drives biodiversity loss and cultural landscape degradation (Lasanta et al. 2017). An estimated 11% of EU agricultural area is at high risk of abandonment for 2015–2030 (Perpiña Castillo et al. 2018). Italy's utilized agricultural area fell by over 20% between 1982 and 2020 (ISTAT 2022), yet this transition remains largely invisible to conventional land-cover products (CORINE, CLMS), which lack the thematic resolution to distinguish unmanaged grassland from early encroachment within fragmented mountain holdings.

This paper presents a Google Earth Engine pipeline translating multi-temporal Sentinel-2 observations (Drusch et al. 2012) into a parcel-level abandonment classification. Two methodological contributions distinguish it: (i) classification anchored directly to cadastral geometry, making outputs directly usable in cadastral and planning workflows, and (ii) time-

synchronous spectral and terrain filters replacing temporally lagged land-use masks.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

The study covers the Monti Prenestini comprensorio (central Italy, ~41.85°N, 12.93°E, 450–950 m a.s.l.), specifically Capranica Prenestina, Castel San Pietro Romano, and Rocca di Cave. The landscape combines sub-Mediterranean dry grasslands, evergreen maquis, and secondary broadleaf forests (Blasi 2010), and includes Natura 2000 SACs "Monte Guadagnolo" (IT6030035) and "Valle delle Cannuccete" (IT6030034).

2.2 Data Sources

The analysis uses the Sentinel-2 L2A archive (S2_SR_HARMONIZED, 2018–2024, Drusch et al. 2012), cloud-masked via Cloud Score+ ($c_s \geq 0.65$, Pasquarella et al. 2023). Annual summer NDVI composites (June–September per-pixel medians) are the primary classification layers. Complementary data include cadastral geometries (Agenzia delle Entrate 2024), ARSIAL soil maps (Regione Lazio 2012), a 10 m DTM (Regione Lazio 2006), and the JRC Global Human Settlement Layer (GHS-BUILT-S, 10 m, 2018, Pesaresi and Politis 2023). Processing uses Google Earth Engine (Gorelick et al. 2017) and Python (geopandas, rasterstats) for cadastral aggregation. Python and JavaScript development was supported by Code, a coding assistant (Anthropic).

2.3 Phenological Basis

The methodology exploits the seasonal contrast where managed swards are drought-dormant by June (NDVI 0.10–0.30), while encroaching evergreen maquis retains chlorophyll (NDVI 0.45–0.70, Tanda et al. 2024). Seasonal Amplitude (summer max minus winter 10th-percentile NDVI) complements static NDVI, decreasing as progressive evergreen canopy dampens the dormancy cycle (Tanda et al. 2024). Secondary Forest (Class 5) is a distinct case, recovering high amplitude through winter leaf-drop of its semi-deciduous canopy but separated from grassland classes by elevated summer NDVI (≥ 0.65 , Figure 1).

2.4 Classification Logic

For classification, phenological layers (summer NDVI, seasonal amplitude) and a Mann–Kendall trend layer (Mann 1945, Kendall 1975, Sen 1968) are combined in a hierarchical cascade. The cascade is structured so that

Figure 1. Summer and winter NDVI profiles (2018–2024) across the gradient. Representative parcels are selected by typicality score: closest to own class centroid and further from other classes.

anthropogenic classes (Artificial, Arable) override vegetative ones. This hierarchical approach ensures that definitive evidence of human modification, such as seasonal ploughing or built-up surfaces, is prioritised over the inherently more variable spectral signals of natural succession. Within vegetative classes, Active Pastoral overrides Forest because in the study area, semi-deciduous broadleaf forest rarely combines amplitude > 0.20 with summer NDVI < 0.55 , making it a signature highly specific to actively managed dry grasslands. Pixels with a significant positive MK trend ($|S| \geq 15$, Sen's slope ≥ 0.005 NDVI yr $^{-1}$, $n = 7$) are then reclassified from Active Pastoral to Initial Encroachment, flagging woody accumulation before the canopy signal saturates. At $n = 7$, $|S| \geq 15$ is the minimum for significance at $\alpha = 0.05$, making this a conservative screen for early encroachment signals (Table 1).

exclude parcels < 200 m 2 , compactness (Polsby–Popper) ≤ 0.06 , majority-Artificial parcels, and parcels with artificial fraction $> 15\%$ to filter suburban houses with gardens. A farmability gate additionally requires slope $< 20^\circ$ (Vigoroso et al. 2019) and non-rocky ARSIAL soil class. The regional land-use survey (Regione Lazio) was rejected due to temporal lag, the study population is instead defined entirely by cadastral geometry and spectral filters.

Accuracy was assessed via six-round stratified desk-verification against multi-temporal Google Earth imagery and GPS field records (2023–2024). Rounds 1–4 ($n = 135, 125, 125, 125$) were calibration rounds (OA 58.5% \rightarrow 76.8%), houses obscured by garden vegetation caused up to 75% of errors in R2–3, motivating GHSL integration. Round 5 ($n = 120$, frozen thresholds) is the internal validation round weighted toward ambiguous classes ($C2 = 35, C3 = 40$), Round 6 ($C2 = 55, \text{Abandoned-only}$) tightens the confidence

Table 1. Classification cascade. Additionally: Class 1 requires slope $< 28^\circ$. (†) Class 3 captures trend-flagged Class 1 pixels and a gap-fill for NDVI 0.55–0.65. Class 6 requires concurrent BLI ($= (B11 - B4)/(B11 + B4)$) spike and NDVI dip in ≥ 2 years, slope $< 15^\circ$. Class 7 uses JRC GHSL to override pixels with built-up surface > 20 m 2 .

Class	Label	Summer NDVI	Amplitude	MK S
0	Uncertain	outside ranges	—	—
1	Active Pastoral	< 0.55	> 0.20	< 15
2	Abandoned	0.15–0.55	> 0.08	—
3	Encroached	> 0.40 or trend (†)	< 0.20	≥ 15 (†)
4	Planted Groves	> 0.45	< 0.15	—
5	Forest	≥ 0.65	—	—
6	Arable (BLI freq.)	> 0.15	—	—
7	Artificial	< 0.25	—	—

2.5 Cadastral Post-Processing and Verification

Uncertain pixels (Class 0) are reassigned to their dominant non-zero vegetative class before aggregation. Each parcel receives the majority class of its constituent 10 m pixels. A 25% plurality rule flags any micro-parcel as Managed if at least one-quarter of pixels are Class 1, threshold intended to reduce false negatives where maintenance signals are spatially partial, and neighbouring trees contaminate parcel edges. Artificial surface detection combines a spectral filter (low NDVI / high BLI) with a JRC GHSL pixel-level override, critical for peri-urban parcels where buildings are obscured by garden canopy. Census filters

interval on Class 2, which showed the lowest vegetative UA (71%) on a modest sample in R5. Inherent limitations include sub-canopy invisibility from nadir images and single-reviewer bias.

3 Results

3.1 Accuracy Assessment

Round 5 achieves OA = 85.8% ($\kappa = 0.82$, 95% CI [78.5%, 91.0%]). Of 17 errors, 8 (47%) are artificial-surface misclassifications, a reduction from 79% in R4, confirming the value of the census-level artificial-fraction filter.

Excluding artificial-surface errors, non-artificial accuracy reaches 92.0% (95% CI [85.4%, 95.7%]). Arable (Class 6, UA = 40%) is unreliable due to rarity (~5 parcels). Round 6 confirms Class 2 UA at 76% (95% CI [64%, 86%]).

3.2 Landscape-Scale Distribution

The study population is 10,290 parcels (~4,387 ha). Secondary Forest dominates (~3,690 ha), Active Pastoral covers ~252 ha (455 parcels). Restoration candidates total ~360 ha: Abandoned Grassland (Class 2, ~110 ha) and Initial

predominantly on well-structured soils (Eutric Cambisols, Luvisols). Table 2 gives structural characteristics by class.

4 Discussion

The 85.8% OA is competitive with supervised ML benchmarks on comparable abandonment tasks (81–87%, Volpi et al. 2023, Morell-Monzó et al. 2023, Liu and Song 2023). The amplitude criterion discriminates managed grassland from transitional scrub even where summer

Table 2. Landscape-scale class distribution.

Class	Label	n	Area (ha)	Slope med.	< 12°	≥ 20°
1	Active	455	252	16.0°	35%	32%
2	Abandoned	110	110	18.3°	25%	46%
3	Encroached	617	250	14.8°	38%	30%
4	Planted Groves	435	84	13.1°	46%	20%
5	Forest	8,658	3,690	22.5°	11%	62%
6	Arable	5	1	8.1°	100%	0%

Figure 2. Parcel-level classification, Monti Prenestini. Outlines: Natura 2000 SAC boundaries.

Encroachment (Class 3, ~250 ha) (Figure 2). Bias-adjusted estimates following Olofsson et al. (2014) yield ~304 ha (95% CI 263–344 ha), 16% below the raw count due to Class 2 commission error, these are lower bounds given the map-stratified design. The farmability synthesis identifies ~165 ha of farmable Classes 2–3 across 4,410 parcels,

NDVI ranges overlap (0.30–0.55), and the MK trend layer provides a velocity indicator absent from static products, helping identify parcels with advancing woody succession. Critically, the rule-based cascade requires no labelled training data and derives thresholds from documented phenological behaviour, which may ease application in similar sub-Mediterranean districts but still requires

external validation, this is important because supervised classifiers can lose recall under spatial transfer (Morell-Monzó et al. 2023). This transparency may also lower the practical barrier for resource-constrained municipal land banks. The resulting cadastral database is already being used within an ongoing local action group platform for abandonment reversal planning. The remaining vegetative confusion lies at the Abandoned–Managed boundary (9 of 17 R5 errors), where grazing spots with favourable microclimate produce ambiguous signatures, R6 confirms Class 2 UA at 76%. The methodology is sensitive to extreme drought (Toreti et al. 2022), which collapses the summer contrast by depressing maquis NDVI toward grassland values.

The slope contrast between classes constitutes the paper's core study-area finding. Classes 1 and 3 occupy similar moderate terrain (median 14.8–16.0°), well within the 20° machinery limit, Abandoned Grassland sits on steeper terrain (median 18.3°, 46% of parcels $\geq 20^\circ$) where thin, rocky substrate constrains recovery. Encroached parcels retain the topsoil and mechanical access that make restoration viable, and their MK trend may indicate advancing woody succession. Under the study-area assumptions used here, this makes encroached land a practical priority class for restoration planning.

5 Conclusion

The cadastral-anchored phenological cascade achieves 85.8% OA ($\kappa = 0.82$) without training data or image segmentation, and identifies encroached land on accessible, machinery-compatible slopes with active successional pressure as a practical restoration priority class for the study area. The modular architecture, with GEE for pixel-level phenology and Python for cadastral aggregation, allows each component to be updated independently as new data sources become available. Transferability to adjacent sub-Mediterranean districts remains to be tested, with the longer-term objective of contributing cadastral-resolution abandonment inventories to agricultural land recovery planning.

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